

A Dissection Framework for the Box Packing Problem, Part I

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Abstract

We develop a combinatorial framework for packing a finite set of axis-parallel rectangles into a rectangular container whose dimensions are not fixed a priori.

The framework encompasses both guillotine and non-guillotine packings and admits a broad class of objective functions, including those arising in strip-packing problems and in the minimization of the bounding-box area or diagonal. The two-dimensional bin-packing problem is not considered.

Each feasible packing is represented by a rectangular dissection. We introduce an equivalence relation on the set of dissections and associate with every equivalence class a combinatorial descriptor, called a *d-code*. We show that the number of equivalence classes is finite and that the correspondence between classes and d-codes is bijective. This yields an explicit enumeration of all admissible d-codes together with their canonical dissections. Since the set of d-codes depends only on the number of rectangles, it can be enumerated independently of any specific instance.

For every d-code, the width and height of the packing are given by two max-plus polynomials in the rectangle dimensions. Structural constraints defining particular variants of the box-packing problem correspond to selecting appropriate subsets of d-codes; guillotine packings form one such subclass.

This paper establishes the combinatorial foundations of the framework; complexity-reduction techniques for individual components will be addressed in a continuation.

Keywords: packing, combinatorial optimization, encoding, max-plus algebra

1 Introduction

Rectangle packing problems arise in numerous applications, including industrial cutting, VLSI layout, and architectural design. The study of cutting patterns

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goes back to the work of Kantorovich [4] and Kantorovich–Zalgaller [5], who formulated guillotine cutting problems within a linear programming framework. Packing problems, including bin packing and variable-size box packing (Section 2), are now known to be NP-hard.

Heuristic approaches are surveyed in [9, 3], while exact algorithms for computing globally optimal packings were proposed in [7, 6, 2]. These methods, however, rely on substantial redundancy and do not provide a structural treatment of guillotine constraints.

In this paper, a geometric-combinatorial framework is introduced for packing a finite family of axis-parallel rectangles into a rectangular container whose dimensions are not fixed a priori. This framework is based on rectangular dissections obtained from packings by an expansion transformation: each rectangle is expanded until it touches either another rectangle or the frame, and the expanded rectangles together with the resulting gaps form a rectangular partition of the frame (see Section 3). The resulting partition is represented as a rectangular dissection in the sense of Brooks–Smith–Stone–Tutte [1], and the original packing is viewed as an embedding of rectangles into the cells of this dissection. This approach extends the zone-based method of [7, 6] and yields a unified structural model encompassing both guillotine and non-guillotine packings. Packing problems that do not admit such a representation, including two-dimensional bin packing, lie outside the scope of this work.

The main result of the paper is a complete combinatorial classification of rectangular dissections. The cuts of each dissection are linearly ordered; an equivalence relation is introduced on the set of dissections, and to every equivalence class and its canonical representative a combinatorial code, called a d -code, is assigned.

Theorem 1.1 (Main Theorem). *Let $n \geq 1$ be an integer. Then the set of equivalence classes of rectangular dissections with n cells is in bijection with the set of admissible d -codes with n cells. Moreover, each d -code uniquely determines a canonical dissection, and the family of all admissible d -codes can be explicitly enumerated independently of the geometric data.*

Each d -code is transformed into max-plus polynomials that compute the dimensions of packings embedded into the dissection associated with that d -code. Structural subclasses, such as guillotine packings, correspond to distinguished subsets of d -codes. Theorem 1.1 provides the combinatorial backbone of the framework developed in this paper. Methods for reducing the family of admissible dissections will be addressed in a continuation.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces notation and basic definitions. Section 3 defines the expansion transformation from packings to rectangular dissections, including guillotine dissections. Section 4 develops a classification of dissections, introduces their combinatorial encoding, called a d -code, and proves a bijection between canonical dissections and d -codes. In addition, a recursive procedure for enumerating all d -codes is presented. In Section 5, normalized packings are defined, it is shown that optimal packings are contained in their family, and max-plus polynomials for computing their

dimensions are derived. In Section 6, a packing model based on the dissection framework is formulated for several variants of the rectangle packing problem. Section 7 summarizes the main results and outlines directions for further research on reducing the complexity of the problem in the proposed setting.

2 Preliminaries

Throughout the paper, all rectangles and segments are axis-parallel, and all rectangles are interior-disjoint. We consider packings into a single bounding box whose dimensions are not fixed in advance. The lower-left corner of the bounding box is placed at the origin $(0, 0)$.

The bounding box of a finite family R of rectangles is the minimal axis-parallel rectangle containing all rectangles of R .

Definition 2.1. The frame of a finite family R of rectangles is the boundary F of the bounding box of R .

Definition 2.2. A box packing is a pair $P = (R, F)$, where R is a finite family of interior-disjoint axis-parallel rectangles and F is the frame of R . The width and height of F are called the dimensions of P . When writing $r \in P$, we mean $r \in R$.

We now recall several definitions and a result from [6].

Definition 2.3. For points $a = (a_x, a_y)$ and $b = (b_x, b_y)$ in \mathbb{R}^2 , we write $a \prec b$ if

$$(a_x < b_x) \wedge (a_y < b_y).$$

Definition 2.4 ([6, Definition 2.1]). The *zone* of a point a is the set

$$z(a) \triangleq \{p = (p_x, p_y) \mid p \prec a\}.$$

Definition 2.5 ([6, Section 2]). The zone of a rectangle r is the zone of its upper-right vertex, denoted $z(r)$.

Theorem 2.6 ([6, Theorem 2.2]). *Let R be a finite set of interior-disjoint axis-parallel rectangles. Then there exists a partial order \prec on R such that for all $r_a, r_b \in R$,*

$$r_a \cap z(r_b) \neq \emptyset \Rightarrow r_a \prec r_b.$$

This relation defines the z -order on R .

3 Packing Expansion and Induced Rectangular Dissection

We introduce a geometric transformation that associates each box packing (Definition 2.2) with a rectangular dissection of its frame F . Each rectangle $r \in R$

is expanded until it touches either another rectangle or the boundary of F . The expanded rectangles together with the resulting empty regions form a rectangular partition of F , which induces a dissection whose cells correspond bijectively to expanded rectangles and empty regions. Guillotine packings yield guillotine dissections. Thus, every packing may be viewed as an embedding of rectangles into a suitable dissection.

3.1 Expanded Rectangles

For each $r \in R$, the *expanded rectangle* \check{r} is obtained by growing r outward until each side touches either the frame F or another expanded rectangle.

Definition 3.1. A rectangle \check{r} is an *expansion* of $r \in R$ if:

1. $r \subseteq \check{r} \subseteq F$;
2. \check{r} is interior-disjoint from all other expanded rectangles;
3. each side of \check{r} meets, with positive length, either the frame F or a *parallel* side of another expanded rectangle.

Every rectangle admits such an expansion. The expansion is not necessarily unique (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Non-uniqueness of rectangle expansions.

3.2 Expanded Packing and Empty Cells

Definition 3.2. The *expanded packing* is $\check{P} = (\check{R}, F)$, where $\check{R} = \{\check{r} : r \in R\}$.

The complement

$$E = F \setminus \bigcup \check{R}$$

consists of finitely many interior-disjoint axis-parallel rectangles, called *empty cells* or *gaps*.

Lemma 3.3. Every gap is an axis-parallel rectangle.

Proof. (Appendix A). □

Thus, $\check{R} \cup E$ forms a rectangular dissection of F in the sense of [1].

3.3 Rectangular Dissection

In this section, a rectangular dissection is defined in terms of horizontal and vertical cuts.

Definition 3.4. The *horizontal cuts* (or simply *h-cuts*) are the connected components of all horizontal sides of rectangles in $\check{R} \cup E$. The *vertical cuts* (or simply *v-cuts*) are defined analogously. All cuts are interior-disjoint and do not meet at endpoints.

Definition 3.5. A *rectangular dissection* (or simply a dissection) $D = (F, (H, V))$ of a frame F is a pair (H, V) of finite sets of *h-cuts* and *v-cuts* such that:

1. all cuts are interior-disjoint;
2. no two endpoints coincide;
3. each cut endpoint lies either on the frame F or on a perpendicular cut.

The cuts partition F into axis-parallel rectangles called *cells*. Hereafter, dissection cells are assumed to be empty unless stated otherwise.

3.4 Guillotine Packings and Guillotine Dissections

In this section, we study the correspondence between guillotine packings and guillotine dissections under expansions.

A *guillotine packing* is defined by recursive full-length cuts that sequentially partition the frame. Guillotine packings induce guillotine dissections, where every cut spans between perpendicular cuts or frame sides.

Lemma 3.6. Every guillotine packing induces a guillotine dissection.

Proof. Immediate from the definitions. □

3.5 Correspondence Between Packing Rectangles and Dissection Cells

Definition 3.7. The *base cut* of a cell is the *h-cut* or *v-cut* whose lower-left endpoint coincides with the lower-left vertex of the cell.

The frame F serves as the base cut of its bottom-left cell. Thus, the number of cells exceeds the number of cuts by one.

Proposition 3.8. Every packing P admits a dissection D such that:

1. each rectangle of P occupies exactly one cell of D ;
2. each cell of D contains at most one rectangle of P ;
3. if P is guillotine, then D is guillotine.

Proof. Follows from Definitions 3.1 and 3.5. □

Remark 3.9 (Clarifying the definitions). The expanded packing \check{P} is a structure derived from the packing P , that is, $\check{P} = \check{P}(P)$. The rectangular dissection D is defined as a structure induced by the expanded packing \check{P} . Accordingly, depending on the context, we write $D = D(\check{P})$ or, for brevity, $D = D(P)$; the latter notation will be used in Subsection 5.1.

4 Equivalence Classes of Dissections and Size-Invariant Descriptors

In this section, we introduce a structural representation of dissections that is independent of metric data. The construction relies on a linear order (Theorem 4.6) imposed on the set of dissection cuts. We then define the notion of a dissection structure, an equivalence relation on the set of such structures, and the canonical representative of each equivalence class, referred to as the normalized dissection. An embedding transformation 5.1 for the rectangles of a given instance is formulated as a transformation of the canonical dissection into one of the dissections within its equivalence class.

We introduce a combinatorial descriptor for each equivalence class, called a d -code, which serves as a size-invariant descriptor of dissections. A bijection is established between the quotient set of dissections and the set of descriptors. Based on this correspondence, we develop an algorithm for enumerating the finite set of all descriptors and, consequently, the quotient set of dissections. An upper bound on the cardinality of the set of d -codes is also derived.

4.1 A Linear Order on Dissection Cuts

Let $D = (F, H, V)$ be a rectangular dissection (Definition 3.5). Denote $C = H \cup V$ the set of all cuts, with $|C| = k$. We regard h -cuts as rectangles of zero height and v -cuts as rectangles of zero width. By Definitions 2.5–2.5 and Theorem 2.6, C admits a well-defined z -order.

Definition 4.1. The z -order induces an orientation on each cut $c \in C$, represented by its ordered endpoints (s, e) , where s is the start point and e is the end point. For h -cuts, s is the left endpoint and e the right endpoint; for v -cuts, s is the lower endpoint and e the upper endpoint.

We introduce closure and opening relations that refine the z -order.

Definition 4.2. A cut c_1 is *closed* by c_2 ($c_1 \dashv c_2$) if an endpoint of c_1 lies on c_2 .

Corollary 4.3. If $c_1 \dashv c_2$, then $s_1 \in z(c_2)$, hence $c_1 \prec c_2$.

Definition 4.4. A cut c_2 is *opened* by c_1 ($c_1 \vDash c_2$) if the start point s_2 of c_2 lies on c_1 .

Corollary 4.5. If $c_1 \vDash c_2$, then $s_1 \in z(c_2)$, hence $c_1 \prec c_2$.

Theorem 4.6. The z -order on $C \cup \{c_0, c_{k+1}\}$ is a linear order.

Proof. It suffices to show every cut $v^* \in C$ has a unique immediate predecessor. Fix a v -cut v^* . Let h_{op}^* and h_{cl}^* be the h -cuts opening and closing v^* , and let v_{opH}^* open h_{cl}^* . By Corollaries 4.3 and 4.5,

$$h_{op}^* \prec v^* \prec h_{cl}^*, \quad v_{opH}^* \prec v^*.$$

Consider two candidates for the immediate predecessor of v^* .

Let h_{cand} be the topmost h -cut closed by v^* , or h_{op}^* if none exists.

Let v_{cand} be the rightmost v -cut preceding v^* and closed by h_{cl}^* , or v_{opH}^* if none exists.

Figure 2: Selecting the immediate predecessor of the v -cut v^* .

Both candidates exist and are unique (Figure 2). The rectangle bounded by h_{cand} , v_{cand} , h_{cl}^* , and v^* contains no other cuts, e.i. it is a cell. Exactly one candidate immediately precedes the other in the z -order; the later one immediately precedes v^* .

Thus, every cut has a unique immediate predecessor, so the z -order is linear. \square

Definition 4.7. A linear ordering of dissection cuts is called a z -chain.

Proposition 4.8. Every prefix of a z -chain of k cuts is a z -chain.

4.2 Equivalence and Normalization of Dissections

Let Δ denote the set of all rectangular dissections. Each cut $c \in C$ is specified by metric data (endpoint coordinates) and structural data (its position in the z -chain). The type of cut is encoded by $t_c \in \{h, v\}$.

The structural position of cut c_i is the tuple

$$\mu_i = (t_i, i, i_{\text{op}}, i_{\text{cl}}), \quad (1)$$

where $i_{\text{op}}, i_{\text{cl}}$ are the indices of cuts opening and closing c_i in the z -chain.

Definition 4.9. A tuple $\mu = (t, i, i_{\text{op}}, i_{\text{cl}})$ is called an *index cut* (idx-cut).

Definition 4.10. The z -chain of idx-cuts $\mathcal{M}[D] = (\mu_1, \dots, \mu_k)$ is the *index code* of dissection D .

Two idx-codes are equivalent if they have the same length and corresponding idx-cuts are componentwise equal:

$$\mathcal{M}_1 \equiv \mathcal{M}_2 \iff k_1 = k_2 \text{ and } \mu_i^{(1)} = \mu_i^{(2)} \text{ for all } i. \quad (2)$$

Definition 4.11. Dissections $D_1, D_2 \in \Delta$ are *equivalent* ($D_1 \sim D_2$) if $\mathcal{M}[D_1] \equiv \mathcal{M}[D_2]$.

Equivalence \sim depends only on structural data and partitions Δ into equivalence classes. Each class admits a unique *normalized representative*.

4.3 Normalized Dissections

The *hv-index* of a cut c_i in a normalized dissection is the number of preceding cuts of the same type plus one:

$$\text{hv}(i) = |\{j < i : t_j = t_i\}| + 1. \quad (3)$$

The endpoints of cut $\mu_i = (t_i, i, i_{\text{op}}, i_{\text{cl}})$ receive coordinates:

For h -cuts:

$$s_i = (\text{hv}(i_{\text{op}}), \text{hv}(i)), \quad e_i = (\text{hv}(i_{\text{cl}}), \text{hv}(i)). \quad (4)$$

For v -cuts:

$$s_i = (\text{hv}(i), \text{hv}(i_{\text{op}})), \quad e_i = (\text{hv}(i), \text{hv}(i_{\text{cl}})). \quad (5)$$

The frame dimensions are $W_D = k_v + 1$, $H_D = k_h + 1$, where k_h, k_v are the numbers of h - and v -cuts. A normalized dissection is denoted \widehat{D} .

Proposition 4.12. For a normalized dissection $\widehat{D}(k)$:

- (i) The last cut $\widehat{D}[k]$ is semi-closed: $\widehat{D}[k] \dashv c_{k+1}$.

Figure 3: Equivalence via normalization.

- (ii) No cut recloses: if $\widehat{D}[i] \dashv \widehat{D}[j]$ then $i < j$ and there is no $l > j$ with $\widehat{D}[i] \dashv \widehat{D}[l]$.

Proof. (i) If $\widehat{D}[k] \dashv c^*$ for some $c^* \in C$, then $\widehat{D}[k] \prec c^*$, contradicting $|C| = k$.

(ii) Suppose $\widehat{D}[i] \dashv \widehat{D}[j]$, $\widehat{D}[i] \dashv \widehat{D}[l]$ with $l > j$. Then $\widehat{D}[l]$ lies above/right of $\widehat{D}[j]$, which lies above/right of $\widehat{D}[i]$, making reclosure impossible by coordinate ordering. \square

The following sets are in bijection:

$$\Delta / \sim \cong \Gamma \cong \mathcal{I}, \quad (6)$$

where Γ is the set of normalized dissections and \mathcal{I} the set of valid idx-codes. Each equivalence class has a unique normalized representative $\widehat{D} \in \Gamma$, which determines a unique idx-code $\mathcal{M}[\widehat{D}] \in \mathcal{I}$.

However, not every syntactic idx-code corresponds to a valid geometric dissection; some encode intersecting cuts.

4.4 Dissection Codes: Definition and Enumeration

We define d -codes as complete structural descriptors of normalized dissections and present a recursive enumeration algorithm.

Consider a sequence of d -cuts

$$q(k) = [d_1, \dots, d_k], \quad d_i = t_i : \tau_i, \quad (7)$$

where $t_i \in \{h, v\}$ is the cut type and $\tau_i \in \mathbb{N}_0$ counts perpendicular cuts closed by d_i .

Define counters σ_i^h, σ_i^v recursively with $\sigma_0^h = \sigma_0^v = 0$:

$$\sigma_i^h = \sigma_{i-1}^h + \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } t_i = h, \\ -\tau_i & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad \sigma_i^v = \sigma_{i-1}^v + \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } t_i = v, \\ -\tau_i & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Definition 4.13. A sequence $q(k)$ is a d -code if $\sigma_i^h \geq 0$ and $\sigma_i^v \geq 0$ for all $i = 1, \dots, k$ (Feasibility Condition, FC). Equivalently,

$$\tau_i \leq \sigma_{i-1}^h \text{ if } t_i = v, \quad \tau_i \leq \sigma_{i-1}^v \text{ otherwise.} \quad (9)$$

Let $Q(k)$ be the set of d -codes of length k . By Proposition 4.8,

Proposition 4.14. Every prefix of a d -code is a d -code.

Theorem 4.15. The sets $\Gamma(k)$ of normalized dissections and $Q(k)$ of d -codes are in bijection.

Proof. ($\Gamma(k) \rightarrow Q(k)$) For $\widehat{D} \in \Gamma(k)$, traverse the z -chain. For cut c_i , count perpendicular cuts it closes (τ_i). The resulting $q(k) = [t_i : \tau_i]$ satisfies FC (9) by coordinate ordering (Propositions 4.12).

($Q(k) \rightarrow \Gamma(k)$) Given $q(k) \in Q(k)$, construct \widehat{D} sequentially. Let n_h, n_v be the numbers of h - and v -cuts; set frame $F = [n_v + 1, n_h + 1]$. Insert cuts c_1, \dots, c_k in z -chain order, where c_i closes exactly τ_i semi-closed perpendicular cuts (last-in, first-out by Lemma below).

Lemma 4.16. Each d -cut closes perpendicular cuts in reverse z -chain order.

Proof. Suppose $c_i^v \prec c_m^v \prec c_j^h$ with c_j^h closing both. Then c_j^h intersects c_m^v , contradicting Definition 3.5. \square

The construction yields a valid normalized dissection satisfying Propositions 4.12. \square

Figure 4 shows construction of $\widehat{D}(6)$ from

$$q(6) = [h : 0, v : 0, h : 1, v : 1, v : 1, h : 1].$$

Algorithms 1–2 convert between idx-codes $\mathcal{I}(k)$ and d -codes $Q(k)$, confirming

$$\mathcal{I}(k) \cong Q(k) \cong \Gamma(k). \quad (10)$$

4.5 Recursive Enumeration

Property 4.14 yields recursive enumeration of $Q(k+1)$: extend each $q(k) \in Q(k)$ by feasible cuts. Let o_h, o_v be semi-closed h - and v -cuts after $q(k)$. Then v -cuts close $0 \leq \tau \leq o_h$ cuts and h -cuts close $0 \leq \tau \leq o_v$ cuts, yielding $o_h + o_v + 2$ extensions.

Since $1 \leq o_h + o_v \leq k$, we have $|Q(k+1)| \leq (k+2)|Q(k)|$, hence

$$|Q(k)| \leq (k+1)!. \quad (11)$$

Figure 4: Construction of $\widehat{D}(6)$ corresponding to $q(6) = [h:0, v:0, h:1, v:1, v:1, h:1]$.

5 Computing Packing Dimensions via Dissection

A rectangular dissection obtained from a packing by the expansion transformation 3.9, in which the packing rectangles are mapped to the dissection cells, with the packing frame dimensions preserved.

The dissection framework reduces the box packing problem to the selection of an optimal filled dissection. We now address the problem of computing the dimensions of a dissection that is filled by the rectangles of a given instance in a prescribed order.

5.1 Embedding Packings into a Dissection

Definition 5.1. The cells of a dissection are partitioned into *active cells* and *optional cells*. An active cell is a cell that is always filled. Such a cell cannot be empty, since in that case it can be removed without changing the packing frame.

An optional cell is a cell that is filled only when needed. Removing such a cell, in general, causes a critical change in the structure of the dissection and packing sizes.

We will analyze the structure of active and optional cells in the next part of the paper.

Algorithm 1 Compute closing indices from d -code

```
1: for  $i = 1$  to  $k$  do
2:    $counter \leftarrow q[i].\tau$ 
3:   for  $j = i - 1$  downto  $1$  do
4:     if  $t_j \neq t_i$  and  $i_{cl,j} = k + 1$  then
5:        $i_{cl,j} \leftarrow i$ 
6:        $counter \leftarrow counter - 1$ 
7:       if  $counter = 0$  then break
8:       end if
9:     end if
10:  end for
11: end for
```

Algorithm 2 Compute opening indices

```
1: for  $i = 1$  to  $k$  do
2:   for  $j = i - 1$  downto  $0$  do
3:     if  $t_j \neq t_i$  and  $i_{cl,j} > i$  then
4:        $i_{op,i} \leftarrow j$ 
5:       break
6:     end if
7:   end for
8: end for
```

Let a dissection D have k cells, of which m are optional and $k - m$ cells are active. Then D can accommodate between $k - m$ and k rectangles. To record the optional cells, each normalized dissection is equipped with a mask.

We assume that each packing rectangle is placed into its designated cell of D according to the mask, aligned with the lower-left corner of that cell.

Since the cuts of a normalized dissection, by Definition 4.3, are constructed with increment 1, which, w.l.o.g., exceeds the maximum size of the packing rectangles, such an embedding is feasible without modifying the dissection (see Fig. 5).

Definition 5.2. *Embedding transformation of a packing* located in a dissection consists of stepwise shifting of the rectangles together with the h-cuts downward and the v-cuts leftward, following the order of the z -chain 4.7.

Fix an h-cut c_H . It is the union of the lower sides of the cells adjacent to c_H from above and the union of the upper sides of the cells adjacent to c_H from below. Both sets of cells lie between c_{opH} and c_{clH} (that is, $c_{opH} \models c_H \dashv c_{clH}$). The cut c_H is shifted downward until it meets the highest top side among the rectangles located in the cells below it. The rectangles in the cells above c_H are translated downward together with the cut as a rigid body, preserving their relative positions.

Rectangles above c_H are not shifted again, since all preceding h-cuts of \widehat{D} lie lower in the z -chain (Figure 5).

Vertical cuts are treated analogously, being shifted leftward.

After processing all cuts, the frame F is rebuilt as the tight bounding box of the resulting rectangles.

Corollary 5.3. The width and height of the embedded packing do not decrease under re-embedding.

Proof. By Definition 5.2, each h-cut (respectively, v-cut) is shifted to the lowest (respectively, leftmost) admissible position. Repeating the embedding transformation does not change the positions of the cuts. \square

Theorem 5.4. *If two copies of a given instance are packed into a pair of equivalent dissections 3.9, and identical rectangles occupy cells with matching indices, then the embedded packings obtained via the embedding transformation are identical.*

Proof. The dissections are equivalent by assumption, so their combinatorial structures coincide. The embedding transformation does not depend on the sizes of the cells. Therefore, the claim follows directly from the definition of the embedding transformation. \square

Definition 5.5. The packing p_q embedded into the dissection q is called normalized and is denoted by p_{qn} .

Theorem 5.6. *Consider the set $P_q = \{p_q\}$ of all packings of a given instance P into dissections belonging to the same equivalence class, and let $p_{qn} \in P_q$ be the normalized one in this class 5.4. Then*

$$p_{qn} = \arg \min_{p_q \in P_q} W(p_q) \quad \text{and} \quad p_{qn} = \arg \min_{p_q \in P_q} H(p_q).$$

Proof. Otherwise, dimensions of p_{qn} could be reduced, which contradicts the Corollary 5.3. \square

Guillotine structure is preserved: cut movements maintain relative incidences encoded by the d -code $q \in Q(k)$.

5.2 Max-Plus Polynomial Expressions for Packing Dimensions

Remark 5.7. The max-plus semiring $\langle \mathbb{R} \cup \{-\infty\}, \max, + \rangle$, also known as the max-plus algebra, gives rise to n -ary polynomials referred to as max-plus polynomials [8].

From Theorem 5.6 it follows that the domain of the box packing problem is the set of normalized packings.

A dissection is represented by two DAG (s - t) networks, $N_w = (V, A_w)$ and $N_h = (H, A_h)$. Here, V is the set of v -cuts, including c_0 and c_{k+1} , and A_w is the set of arcs, each corresponding to a cell and directed from the cut on its left

Figure 5: Embedding transformation: normalized dissection (left) to minimal packing (right).

side to the cut on its right side. The network N_h is defined analogously using the set of h -cuts H and arcs A_h directed from the lower cut of each cell to its upper cut. The arc weights in N_w and N_h are parameters equal to the width and height of the rectangle embedded in the corresponding cell.

Theorem 5.8. *The rectangles corresponding to the arcs of a longest path in N_w (respectively, N_h) touch their predecessors along that path.*

Proof. Otherwise, the sum of the widths (respectively, heights) of the rectangles would be smaller than the length of the longest path, which contradicts the definition of a longest path. \square

Theorem 5.9. *The width and height of the packing coincide with the lengths of the longest paths in N_w and N_h , respectively.*

Proof. This follows immediately from Theorem 5.8. \square

Definition 5.10. Each arc in N_w or N_h is determined by three cut indices: the index of the cut defining the cell and the indices of a directed pair of cuts, either the left and right cuts or the lower and upper cuts.

Proposition 5.11. Each pair of consecutive cuts c_i, c_{i+1} in the z -chain defines a unit cell bounded by four cuts

$$c_{\text{op}(i)} \prec c_i \prec c_{i+1} \prec c_{\text{cl}(i+1)},$$

where $c_{\text{op}(i)} \vDash c_i$ and $c_{i+1} \dashv c_{\text{cl}(i+1)}$.

Proof. Each cell is defined by its base cut 3.7 at the lower-left vertex. Consequently, two sides of this cell lie along the cuts c_i and $c_{\text{op}(i)}$. The cut c_{i+1} is

the immediate successor of c_i ; by symmetry, the upper-right corner of the cell is formed by c_{i+1} and $c_{cl(i+1)}$. Otherwise, the rectangle bounded by this quadruple of cuts would contain another cut c^a satisfying $c_i \prec c^a \prec c_{i+1}$, contradicting the consecutiveness of the indices i and $i + 1$. \square

The indices of the opening cut $c_{op(i)}$ and the closing cut $c_{cl(i+1)}$ are contained in the index code of a dissection.

The indices of the cuts bounding a cell are partitioned by type into a pair of vertical cuts and a pair of horizontal cuts. Consequently, each cell of the dissection defines two arcs, one in N_w and one in N_h .

Since the arc weights of the network are parameters, any path may become the longest one. Therefore, it is natural to define the longest path as the maximum over all paths.

The width of a dissection in the network N_w is expressed by the max-plus polynomial W_p (Remark 5.7). The polynomial W_p is defined as the maximum of the lengths of all s - t paths in N_w , where the length of each path is the sum of the weights of its arcs. The polynomial is then algebraically transformed to eliminate repeated operands. The polynomial W_p is invariant with respect to the parameters of any particular instance and is stored in a database. The height of a dissection is defined analogously for N_h by the polynomial H_p .

We now illustrate this framework using the following example:

$$q_e(9) = [v:0, h:0, h:0, h:1, v:2, v:0, v:1, h:1, h:1]. \quad (12)$$

The FC (9) holds for every dissection cut, with respect to its perpendicular open cuts:

$$\sigma_1^h = 0, \sigma_2^v = 1, \sigma_3^v = 1, \sigma_4^v = 0, \sigma_5^h = 1, \sigma_6^h = 1, \sigma_7^h = 0, \sigma_8^v = 2, \sigma_9^v = 1. \quad (13)$$

Thus, $q_e(9)$ in (12) is a d -code.

We use the d -code and the idx -code to determine the closing and opening cut indices, c_{cl_i} and c_{op_i} , respectively. These indices are collected in the second and third rows of Table 1.

Cut index	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
c_{cl_i}	4	7	5	5	$k1$	9	8	$k1$	$k1$
c_{op_i}	0	1	1	0	2	2	0	6	5

Table 1: The idx -code for $q_e(9)$.

From Proposition 5.11 and the subsequent derivations, the cut indices for the boundaries of each cell are assigned (Table 2).

The nodes of the network N_w correspond to the v -cuts extracted from the d -code $q_e(9)$ 12 : c_0 (source), c_1 , c_5 , c_6 , c_7 , and c_{k1} (sink). Each cell defines

Cell index	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Left-right cuts	0-1	1-7	1-5	1-5	0-5	5-6	6-7	7- k_1	6- k_1	5- k_1
Bottom-top cuts	0-4	0-2	2-3	3-4	4-0	2-9	2-8	0-8	8-9	9- k_1

Table 2: Boundary indices for $q_e(9)$.

an arc in N_w , connecting the left and right boundaries of the corresponding dissection cell. Here is a list of the arcs:

$$\begin{aligned}
& b_0(0, 1), b_1(1, 7), b_2(1, 5), b_3(1, 5), b_4(0, 5), b_5(5, 6), \\
& b_6(6, 7), b_7(7, k_1), b_8(6, k_1), b_9(5, k_1).
\end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

We enumerate all paths from the source node St to the sink node En . To describe adjacency between cells, we use the notation $i \xrightarrow{n} j$ to indicate that the i -th and j -th cells are connected via the n -th cut. The length of each arc b_i is denoted by w_i . Table 3 lists all such paths together with their corresponding lengths.

The packing width W_p is defined as the maximum path length in N_w . This value is obtained by substituting the actual dimensions of the packed rectangles into the operands of W_p .

We represent W_p algebraically as a max-plus polynomial, where the operations max and $+$ play the roles of addition and multiplication, respectively. For brevity, we denote max by \oplus and $+$ by \odot .

$(St \xrightarrow{0} 0 \xrightarrow{1} 1 \xrightarrow{7} 7 \xrightarrow{k_1} En)$	$[w_0 + w_1 + w_7]$
$(St \xrightarrow{0} 0 \xrightarrow{1} 2 \xrightarrow{5} 5 \xrightarrow{6} 6 \xrightarrow{7} 7 \xrightarrow{k_1} En)$	$[w_0 + w_2 + w_5 + w_6 + w_7]$
$(St \xrightarrow{0} 0 \xrightarrow{1} 2 \xrightarrow{5} 5 \xrightarrow{8} 8 \xrightarrow{k_1} En)$	$[w_0 + w_2 + w_5 + w_8]$
$(St \xrightarrow{0} 0 \xrightarrow{1} 2 \xrightarrow{5} 9 \xrightarrow{k_1} En)$	$[w_0 + w_2 + w_9]$
$(St \xrightarrow{0} 0 \xrightarrow{1} 3 \xrightarrow{5} 5 \xrightarrow{6} 6 \xrightarrow{7} 7 \xrightarrow{k_1} En)$	$[w_0 + w_3 + w_5 + w_6 + w_7]$
$(St \xrightarrow{0} 0 \xrightarrow{1} 3 \xrightarrow{5} 5 \xrightarrow{8} 8 \xrightarrow{k_1} En)$	$[w_0 + w_3 + w_5 + w_8]$
$(St \xrightarrow{0} 0 \xrightarrow{1} 3 \xrightarrow{5} 9 \xrightarrow{k_1} En)$	$[w_0 + w_3 + w_9]$
$(St \xrightarrow{0} 4 \xrightarrow{5} 5 \xrightarrow{6} 6 \xrightarrow{7} 7 \xrightarrow{k_1} En)$	$[w_4 + w_5 + w_6 + w_7]$
$(St \xrightarrow{0} 4 \xrightarrow{5} 5 \xrightarrow{8} 8 \xrightarrow{k_1} En)$	$[w_4 + w_5 + w_8]$
$(St \xrightarrow{0} 4 \xrightarrow{5} 9 \xrightarrow{k_1} En)$	$[w_4 + w_9]$

Table 3: Computing cells bounding indices for (12).

We derive

$$\begin{aligned}
 W_p = & w_0 \odot w_1 \odot w_7 & (15) \\
 & \oplus w_0 \odot w_2 \odot w_5 \odot w_6 \odot w_7 \\
 & \oplus w_0 \odot w_2 \odot w_5 \odot w_8 \\
 & \oplus w_0 \odot w_2 \odot w_9 \\
 & \oplus w_0 \odot w_3 \odot w_5 \odot w_6 \odot w_7 \\
 & \oplus w_0 \odot w_3 \odot w_5 \odot w_8 \\
 & \oplus w_0 \odot w_3 \odot w_9 \\
 & \oplus w_4 \odot w_5 \odot w_6 \odot w_7 \\
 & \oplus w_4 \odot w_5 \odot w_8 \\
 & \oplus w_4 \odot w_9.
 \end{aligned}$$

We rearrange the polynomial in (15) and get

$$W_p = w_0 \odot w_1 \odot w_7 \oplus (w_0 \odot (w_2 \oplus w_3) \oplus w_4) \odot (w_9 \oplus w_5 \odot (w_8 \oplus w_6 \odot w_7)). \quad (16)$$

Similarly, we express the packing height by a polynomial H_p .

$$H_p = h_4 \odot (h_0 \oplus h_1 \odot h_2 \odot h_3) \oplus h_9 \odot (h_1 \odot h_5 \oplus h_8 \odot (h_1 \odot h_6 \oplus h_7)). \quad (17)$$

Figure 6: The normalized dissection for (12). Cut indices are shown in black, and cell indices in red.

Figure 6 illustrates the normalized dissection corresponding to the d -code in (12). The polynomials W_p and H_p serve as the objective function and the constraint, respectively, for the optimal rectangle embedding problem defined on this dissection.

For the strip packing problem, one of the polynomials W_p or H_p is designated as the objective function, while the other is imposed as a feasibility constraint, when embedding an instance into this.

The domain of the problem consists of all permutations of the rectangles.

The d -code, along with the polynomials $W_p(q)$ and $H_p(q)$, is precomputed offline and stored in a dedicated database.

6 Dissection-Based Optimization Models

Let $S_k = \{q\}$ denote the set of all dissections with $n \geq k$ active and optional cells 5.1, where k rectangles are embedded via mask in a dissection. 5.1

Rectangle permutation $\omega_k \in \Omega_k$ determines embedding into cells ordered by the z -chain. Packing dimensions are given by max-plus polynomials $W_p(q, \omega_k), H_p(q, \omega_k)$ (Section 5).

The general box packing problem is

$$\min_{(q, \omega_k) \in S_k \times \Omega_k} \varphi(W_p, H_p) \quad \text{s.t.} \quad \gamma(W_p, H_p) \leq 0, \quad (18)$$

where φ is the objective and $\gamma \leq 0$ encodes constraints.

This framework yields classical variants:

(i) *Strip packing:*

$$\min W_p \quad \text{s.t.} \quad H_p \leq \widehat{H}, \quad (19)$$

$$\text{or} \quad \min H_p \quad \text{s.t.} \quad W_p \leq \widehat{W}. \quad (20)$$

(ii) *Minimum area:*

$$\min W_p \cdot H_p. \quad (21)$$

(iii) *Minimum diagonal:*

$$\min W_p^2 + H_p^2. \quad (22)$$

Guillotine dissections form a structured subclass $S_k^G \subset S_k$, enumerable via d -code restrictions (Definition 4.13).

7 Conclusion

We have established a complete combinatorial classification of rectangular dissections and applied it to the variable-size box packing problem. The main results are:

- (i) Every packing embeds into a rectangular dissection via expansion (Theorem 3.8). The embedding preserves dimensions and guillotine structure.
- (ii) Dissections are classified via d -codes $Q(k)$ (Definition 4.13). The quotient set $\Delta / \sim \cong Q(k) \cong \Gamma(k)$ is enumerated recursively (Theorem 4.15), depending only on k .

- (iii) Packing dimensions are max-plus polynomials $W_p(q), H_p(q)$ (Section 5), fully determined by the d -code $q \in Q(k)$.

The dissection database $\{q \in Q(k)\}_{k \geq 1}$ enables instance-independent pre-computation. Optimization reduces to evaluating $W_p(q, \omega_k), H_p(q, \omega_k)$ over $q \in Q(k), \omega_k \in \Omega_k$ (Section 6).

Future work will develop complexity-reduction techniques.

Acknowledgments

The authors thank A. M. Shteinberg for valuable discussions and constructive advice. We gratefully remember the contributions of the late V. A. Zalgaller and I. V. Romanovsky for their consultations and support.

Appendix A Proof of Lemma 3.3

Lemma 3.3. Every gap is an axis-parallel rectangle.

Proof. Assume for contradiction that a non-rectangular gap exists, containing a vertex p_0 with internal angle 270° (Figure 7a). Such a vertex cannot lie on any expanded rectangle side by Definition 3.1.

Figure 7: We study the region $\{p_0, p_1, p_3, p_5, p_4, p_2\}$ and show that it must be rectangular.

Consider the configuration around p_0 with five expanded rectangles R_0, R_1, \dots, R_4 :

- R_0 touches R_1, R_2 along bottom/left sides (density condition).

- R_1 : leftmost rectangle above R_0 , $p_1 =$ top-left vertex of R_1 .
- R_2 : lowest rectangle right of R_0 , $p_2 =$ bottom-right vertex of R_2 .
- R_3 : highest rectangle right of R_1 , $p_3 =$ top-right vertex of R_3 .
- R_4 : rightmost rectangle above R_2 , $p_4 =$ top-right vertex of R_4 .
- p_5 : intersection of top side through R_3 and right side through R_4 .

Consider region $S = \{p_0, p_1, p_3, p_5, p_4, p_2\}$.

(i) No rectangle lies entirely inside S . Otherwise, its top-right vertex would coincide with p_1 or p_2 , contradicting maximality of R_1, R_2 (Figure 7b).

(ii) No rectangle intersects S along $[p_4, p_5]$ or $[p_3, p_5]$. Expansion would force it to touch R_1 from left or R_2 from below, contradicting R_3, R_4 (Figure 7c).

(iii) No rectangle touches both R_3 (right) and R_4 (above). Expansion would force p_0 onto an side, contradicting the 270° angle (Figure 7d).

Thus S contains no rectangles, so p_0 lies on an expanded rectangle side, contradicting the assumption. All symmetric cases follow analogously. \square

References

- [1] R. L. Brooks, C. A. B. Smith, A. H. Stone, and W. T. Tutte. The dissection of rectangles into squares. *Duke Mathematical Journal*, 7:312 – 340, 1940.
- [2] Sándor P. Fekete and Jörg Schepers. A new exact algorithm for general orthogonal d-dimensional knapsack problems. In *Algorithms — ESA '97*, pages 144–156, 1997.
- [3] Alvaro Luiz Neuenfeldt Júnior, Elsa Silva, Matheus Binotto Francescatto, Carmen Brum Rosa, and Julio Cezar Mairesse Siluk. The rectangular two-dimensional strip packing problem real-life practical constraints: A bibliometric overview. *Computers & Operations Research*, 137:105521, 2022.
- [4] L. V. Kantorovich. Mathematical methods of organizing and planning production. *Management Science*, 6(4):366–422, 1960. English republishing of the work in Russian, 1939.
- [5] L. V. Kantorovich and V. A. Zalgaller. *Calculations for Rational Cutting of industrial Materials*. Lenizdat, Leningrad, In Russian, 1 edition, 1951.
- [6] A. I. Lipovetskii. A geometrical approach to computation of the optimal solution to the rectangle packing problem. *American Mathematical Society Translations*, 222:93–110, 2008. English republishing of the work in Russian, 1988.
- [7] A. I. Lipovetsky. Algorithms for non-guillotine rectangular cutting. In *Proceeding of Mathematical methods for cutting and packing problems in CAD systems*, 1988. Ufa, Russian edition.

- [8] Mehryar Mohri. Semiring frameworks and algorithms for shortest-distance problems. *Journal of Automata, Languages and Combinatorics*, 7(3):321–350, 2002.
- [9] José Fernando Oliveira, Alvaro Neuenfeldt Júnior, Elsa Silva, and Maria Antónia Carravilla. A survey on heuristics for the two-dimensional rectangular strip packing problem. *Pesquisa Operacional*, 36:197–226, 2016.